

**Assessment of a 49 Year Old Sewage Pond for Rehabilitation through
Bioremediation**

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**A dissertation submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the degree of
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Statement of Originality

The investigation was carried out in fulfilment of the Master of Science in Solid Waste and Resource Management in the Civil Engineering Department, PNG University of Technology. I hereby declare that this submission is my own work and to the best of my knowledge, it contains no materials previously published or written by another person or material which have been excepted for the award of any other higher degree at PNGUOT or elsewhere, except where duly cited and acknowledge.

Signed:

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to be 'Chub', written over a horizontal line. There are some faint marks above the line, possibly from a stamp or another signature.

Date: 30 March 2022

Abstract

The study evaluates the effects of plant species in the sewage pond area. The research design employed statistics and primary data for the findings. The data were collected using qualitative and quantitative instruments, which focused on actual transect data, survey questionnaires and field observations. The primary data were processed using spreadsheets on MS Excel and MS Word as well as SPSS software. The research evaluated environmental hazards to the nearby communities, the effect of overflow, contaminated stream, soil, air and heavy metals uptake by plants as the risk to surrounding livelihood and lifestyle, and the effect of plants, behaviours and perceptions. The plant abilities evaluation was based on leaf and stem evaluation impact. The research into sewage ponds shows that plants do neutralize heavy metals after the effluent pond is a priority and needs attention for the sustainability of the pond project development in Unitech is required. A study into the sewage impact reveals that pond input, environmental impact, social impact and economic impact of sewage ponds are classified as a priority and need attention. The evaluation shows that plants benefit from both affluence and soil. The research reveals the likelihood that farmers using nearby land may have received the sewage pond effluent into the food chain. The study into sewage assessment perception, views and reaction show the community grievances and complaints generated by the effects of lack of pond maintenance. The research recommends broader pond maintenance, institution consultation and participation in rehabilitation project development.

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Abbreviations

APHA	American Public Health Association
As	Arsenic
BOD	Biological Oxygen Demand
Cd	Cadmium
Cr	Chromium
Cu	Copper
MPL	Minimum Permissible Level
NATSL	National Analytical and Testing Services Laboratory
P1	Pond 1
P2	Pond 2
P3	Pond 3
PNGUOT	Papua New Guinea University of Technology
RW	Raun Wara (Control Site)
SPSS	Statistical Package for Social Science
UASL	Unitech Analytical Service laboratory
USP	Unitech Sewerage Pond
WSP	Waste Stabilization Pond

List of Appendages

1. Soil sample laboratory analysis data
2. Biological oxidation demand (BOD) laboratory analysis data
3. Plants sample laboratory analysis data
4. Water sample laboratory analysis data.

Chapter One

1. INTRODUCTION

Wastewater stabilization ponds (WSPs) have been used to treat wastewater for over 3,000 years (EPA, United States Environmental protection Agency, 2011). The first recorded construction of a pond system WSP in the U.S. was in San Antonio, Texas, in 1901 (Gloyna, 1971). The treatment and disposal of wastewater is an expensive and environmentally-sensitive problem worldwide (Rezania, S., Fadhil, Md. D. M., Taib, S., M., Dahalan, F., A., Songip, A. L. S., Kamyab, H, (2015). For many years the massive issue is still cladding the globe. The residue will escalate, and new modern automation of sewage treatment facilities will establish following municipal waste disposal quality standards (Adeniji, 2004). Most traditional methods such as landfill, incineration, composting, and waste disposal recycling have been a struggle by developing countries to find cost-effective and creative sustainable ways in response to public pressure, regulatory bodies and the environment (Ruicheng. D, Xiao, C. Zibin. D, Haona. G, Xin. L, Xiaoying. L, Xialan. Z, 2019). With the alarming rate of the growing population and industrial development, wastewater generation has increased and is expected to significantly increase in the future. Wastewater stabilization ponds play an essential role in urban economies using infrastructure development and human population growth. Most economic activities occur in urban areas; subsequently, appropriate waste management may transform urban livelihood. A desirable option for sustainable development is reducing, recycling and reusing waste rather than incineration, land spreading and landfilling (Ahmed, Diaz, Faaji, Gao and Hasimoto, 2007). Generally, sludge is moral as a thick, delicate, damp mud or a thick blend of fluid with crystal-like solid components, which is the end product of a sewer system or an industrial plant. Sludge contains at least 96% water and causes inevitable environmental problems and health hazards (Andreoli, Sperling and Fernandes, 2007). These are world trends concerning sludge management in terms of conversion of produced sludge into valuable materials and not harmful (to human beings. A past study showed that the amounts of municipal waste produced and disposed of or reused are not subsequently documented (Abdel-Fattah, G.M., Rabie, G.H., Lamis, D.S. and Rabab, A.M, 2016).

The sewage lagoon at Papua New Guinea University of Technology (PNGUOT) 49 years ago seems almost full and is currently contributing to environmental problems such as air pollution in the neighbourhood. Such environmental problems that may likely occur are; streams (river)

contamination, soil contamination, odour (air pollution) and heavy metal uptake by plants which may ultimately end up in the food chain. Numerous field observations have indicated that the lagoons overflow into main waterways during heavy storms. Physical field observation also indicated that the by-product of the wastewater treatment system (known as sludge) had reached the lagoon's surface. In some instances, the dissolved sludge overflows while encountering channel blockages. This research aims to figure out a support strategy to rehabilitate the Unitech sewage lagoon. The amount of treatment required in the lagoon depends entirely on the US Environmental Protection Agency standard, which is set for the lagoon effluent. The suggested effluent criteria state that the quality of waste should not impair the appearance of the stream, and deleterious toxic substances should not be discharged under the specific effluent levels set. For example, >5mg/L dissolved oxygen (DO), <20 mg/L biochemical oxidation demand (BOD), <30 mg/L suspended solids (SS), 6.5 to 9.2 of pH and <1000 CFU/100 mL of *E. coli* (before chlorination). These standards are generally accepted for the design of sewage treatment by lagoons and discharge into inland waterways in PNG (Willing and Partners, 1977). However, exceeding a specific effluent level will most likely have a greater impact on the surrounding environment. Michael et al. (2017) indicated that the specific effluent level is much higher in the outlet pond (effluent). From this argument, this study aims to formulate new methods to minimize pollution and environmental degradation concerning sludge buildup in the lagoons. In addition, the study also aimed at using sewage sludge as a substitute for concrete products in the construction industry.

Artificial sewage lagoons may cause ecosystem degradation and health problems regarding poor management in developing countries. This challenging issue needs to be addressed through infrastructure development and rehabilitation that is suitable, sustainable, efficient, and effective for human use. Sewage ponds in towns and cities need to be planned to be economically viable, socially inclusive, and environmentally sustainable. The social issues and infrastructure constraints on waste generation promote desirable management behaviour and urban waste avoidance. In the changing world today, environmental pollution in air, soil, and water is a critical problem that needs immediate attention. This research will outline sustainable support strategies to reduce possible pollution and environmental hazards from the Unitech sewage pond (USP). This research aims to utilize potential plants for the uptake of heavy metals. Identified plants were growing in the lagoon's vicinity and tested for characterization.

1.1. Objectives

This study aims to assess the plant species living in the 49 -year old sewage pond as a material for rehabilitation through bioremediation. It specifically answers to (1) Figuring out soil conditions and their concentration adjacent to sewage lagoons, (2) Identifying high concentration factors of heavy metals in plant leaves, and (3) Identifying potential plant species capable of bioremediation purposes.

1.2. Study Site

The domestic sewage pond is located at the PNG University of Technology, Lae, Papua New Guinea ($6^{\circ}41'54.87''S$; $145^{\circ}58'58.65''E$). The establishment of the ponds was around the 1970s. Wastewater from the University community is released into three ponds parallel to one another. Biological treatment is given before it releases into the environment, as shown below on the aerial photograph map.

Figure: 1, Map shows the location of Lae in relation to Papua New Guinea.

Figure: 2 Location map and Google image of study site at PNGUOT sewage ponds.

1.3. Basis of Study

Michael and co-workers (2017) established that the effluent from the Unitech sewerage ponds contained levels of heavy metals higher than the minimum permissible limits (MPL) instead of concentrations below the MPL. The same authors suggested that this could be due to plant macrophyte senescence. The study is geared to prove that by analysing the heavy metals in the plants at the sewerage pond site.

Chapter Two

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The developing nation needs to preserve its environment due to the alarming rate of environmental degradation. Protecting the environment has drawn much consideration from the scholarly world and businesses, particularly for forms including toxin strong squander reusing (Rotriguez & Holanda, 2015). It shows from the reality that utilising waste contributes to environmental assurance and economic advancement. Untreated waste gushing in towns and cities is one of the significant issues with biological system contamination (Rono, A. K., & Wanjala, P. M. (2018). Hence, it contributed to high amounts of toxins and strong waste in the water treatment plant and sewage framework (Richter, 1991; Bernardo & Dantas, 2005). Commonly this civil slime closes up at the closest water framework causing issues such as changes to marine life, doubling the sum of solids, alteration within the colour and turbidity, sedimentation, increment concentration of the metal from the squander and may cause open wellbeing hazard (Olivera, 2004). Moreover, the issue here is to discover an ideal resting place (biological goal) for the waste slime to fit in biologically.

Few studies found the generation of cement bricks by consolidating sewage sludge (Silva, 2009). It has driven the affirmation that little has been known about metropolitan sludge at open sewage lakes. It has raised the question of which inviting biological environment the sewage sludge might be rested securely and for all time without causing wellbeing dangers. In expansion, the development of waste getting to be a suitable elective for the transfer of waste of different sorts and beginning, compared with the conventional strategies (Olivera, 2004; Turgut & Algin, 2007; Alzboon K. K, Al-Harashsheh M., Hani F. H., 2010; Pinheiro & Holanda, 2013; Begum, Gandhimathi, Ramesh and Nidheesh, 2013). Their studies pointed out the plausibility of consolidating sewage sludge into sludge–cement brick for civil development as one way to utilize the sludge and empty the ponds for new intakes.

There are few studies on plants in open sewage zones and their take-up of overwhelming metals within the phytoremediation process. As implied, third-world nations with destitute financial conditions are to look at natural frameworks to treat the environment and sanitary issues (Deng, Y. Su, Y.Wang, X. and Zhu, Z.,2007) in wastewater stabilization lakes. Concurring to (Abdel – Rauof, N., Al-Homaidan, A.A. and Ibraheem, I.B.M., 2012), a few nations utilize a stabilization lake as a natural process that is environmentally economical, fetched effective,

reliable, and simple to function. The anaerobic and facultative lake is the storage place where biochemical oxygen demand occurs. Fundamentally, these frameworks are subordinate to each other where organisms and microscopic organisms evacuate supplements and heavy metals (Kiran, B., Kaushik, A. and Kaushik, C.P, 2007; Pandi, M., Sashirekha, V. and Swamy, M., 2009; (Afkar, A., Ababna, H. and Fathi, A. A., 2010; (Chen, C., Chang, H., Kao, P., Pan, J., 2012). Numerous vascular plants out there need to be well documented in terms of overwhelming metal take-up. In any case, exceptionally little has been known about those plants. Michael and Reid (2018) contented that one or more water tolerant vascular plants are prevailing because of the mechanism they have to take up overwhelming metals. A few of these plants were examined in the past (e.g., Anushee, 2005, (Rezania, S., Ponraj, M., Din, M. D. Md, Chelliapan, S. and Sairan, D. Md 2016); (Michael, P. S., Fitzpatrick, W. R. and Reid, R., 2017) ; (Obogu, M., Odokuma, L O. and Akponah, E., 2018). Besides, past studies have appeared that exceptionally little was known about such plants in tropical climate conditions in open sewage lakes. Michael, P. S., Haua, B. and Sabogi. M. (2019), had pointed out that the concentration of overwhelming metal at the outlet lakes is much higher than at the inlet lakes. Further documented that phytoremediation of overwhelming metals by *E. Crassipes* and other prevailing plant species at the lake has deteriorated back to the lakes once they senescence or leachate from adjacent mechanical centres has contributed to high concentration at outlet lakes. These come about have suggestions for managing sewage wastewater stabilization lakes overwhelmed by plant macrophytes, particularly beneath the tropical climate (Michael, P. S. Haua, B., and Sabogi, M., 2019). Understanding why the concentration at the outlet pond is higher than in the inlet sewage ponds, the concentration ought to be much lower than in the inlet lakes. Is it because of the dead plant's biomass amassing, leachate or surface water flood amid stormy seasons? These discoveries and questions have raised the crevice for a further investigation to demonstrate the presumption.

2.1. Pond Types

Waste stabilization ponds consist of artificial basins involving a solitary or a few arrangements of anaerobic, facultative or development ponds (Ramadan, Hamzeh, Ponce and Victor, 2016). The oxygen levels vary with the three unique types of sewerage treatment ponds. Anaerobic waste adjustment ponds have almost no disintegrated oxygen, so anaerobic conditions win. The

second sort of lake, facultative adjustment ponds, continue a high-impact surface territory over an anaerobic benthic habitat (Ashworth, 2011). Maturation ponds offer oxygen-consuming conditions, from the surface to the base. According to Von Sperling (2005) and USEPA (2011), the principle on set-ups of ponds frameworks are an Anaerobic pond followed by a facultative pond, followed by effluent.

If an anaerobic pond is available, part of the suspended solids from the wastewater settles, eliminating the natural issue (BOD) contributed by these solids. Moreover, a portion of the disintegrated natural issue is eliminated by anaerobic assimilation. In the facultative pond, a large portion of the rest of the BOD is eliminated essentially by the heterotrophic microscopic organisms that get oxygen from the photosynthesis embraced by the growth of greens or plants. The primary capacity of the tertiary stage in development ponds is the evacuation of microorganisms, although it might likewise aid supplementation (for example, nitrogen) (Ashworth, 2011). However, nitrogen obsession with green growth living in adjustment pond frameworks may expand nitrogen levels in the effluent (von Sperling, (2007).

2.1.1. Anaerobic Ponds

Anaerobic ponds get crude wastewater. They have a little surface zone contrasted with facultative ponds and are more profound (typically 3.0 to 5.0 m). The profundity diminishes the impact of oxygen creation by photosynthesis, prompting anaerobic conditions. Contingent upon stacking and climatic conditions, these ponds can eliminate between half to 66% of the influent BOD. It altogether diminishes the heap of wastewater that goes to the facultative pond and, along these lines, diminishes their required size (von Sperling, 2005). Anaerobic ponds have the hindrance of conceivably delivering rancid gases. It incorporates hydrogen sulphide with a scent of rotten eggs if the framework has operational problems (Morris, 2010). The principal lake biome in a progression of adjustment pond processes the putrescible solids suspended in the wastewater. Anaerobic ponds permit solids to settle down at the base as ooze. This settling eliminates a segment of the natural particulate material (Morris, 2010). A massive portion of the settled solids will aggregate near wastewater entering the lake. Thus, an anaerobic pond must be far more profound than a high-impact or facultative pond. The profundity diminishes the oxygen levels so anaerobic microbes can proficiently process the waste (Morris, 2010). Anaerobic ponds contain anaerobic life forms which can separate complex natural waste into essential intensifiers that are less unsafe to the environment

(Cincinnati, 2010). Because anaerobic living species can flourish in warm temperatures, anaerobic ponds are inappropriate in mild or cold atmospheres. Muck collects at the lower part of the anaerobic pond and should be eliminated at regular intervals.

2.1.2. Facultative Ponds

Facultative adjustment ponds that get crude wastewater are called essential facultative ponds. It is an optional facultative pond when it gets wastewater that has just been treated in an anaerobic pond. Facultative adjustment ponds may likewise be utilized for treatment following different treatment cycles, for example, up-flow anaerobic slime cover (UASB) reactors, oxidation discard or circulated air through tidal ponds. Unlike anaerobic ponds, facultative ponds are shallower (1.5 to 2.5 m profound) and have a much bigger surface territory. The surface zone is significant because it permits climatic oxygen to break up and daylight radiation to enter the water. It takes into account photosynthetic movement to happen, which creates more oxygen.

In many ponds, the microorganisms and green growth are required to expand the deterioration of natural issues and the evacuation of other pollutants (Cincinnati, 2010). Algae produce oxygen (photosynthesis) and furthermore devour oxygen (breath), yet they leave an overabundance of oxygen that would be then able to be utilized by high-impact microbes for breath and the cycles of oxidation (or adjustment) of the human waste in the wastewater. Some spineless creatures are available in the ponds where they control the number of inhabitants in green growth, which settles to the bottom (Cincinnati, 2010). Heavy algal development may impede daylight from entering the lake. It reduces the potential for photosynthesis to contribute oxygen to the lake. In sewage treatment, frameworks are made out of anaerobic ponds followed by facultative ponds, generally speaking, BOD expulsion efficiencies are between 75 and 85%. Higher efficiencies are hard to accomplish because the profluent contains high groupings of natural particulate matter, such as green growth, usually delivered during treatment. The slope containing the silt layer in the pond goes through anaerobic assimilation and may aggregate for quite a while without requiring evacuation.

2.1.3. Maturation Ponds

Some additional evacuation of natural matter and various contaminants might be accomplished in the development pond. These ponds are possibly remembered for the treatment line when high efficiencies of microbe evacuation are required, either for release of the treated emanating in surface water bodies or for use for water systems or hydroponics. They are generally utilized after the facultative pond; however, they may likewise follow other treatment measures, for example, up-flow anaerobic Sludge blanket (UASB) reactors (Chernicharo, 2007). They could likewise be put after an initiated ooze measure.

Development ponds must be shallow (around 1.0 m profundity or less) with an extraordinary surface zone so more oxygen can break into the water giving the microbes enough oxygen to appropriately function (Morris, 2010). Shallow lakes profit from high photosynthetic movement emerging from the infiltration of sun-oriented radiation. The pH directly results from exceptional photosynthesis, and bright radiation entrance happens in the upper layers. Both of these variables advance the evacuation of pathogenic microbes and infections. Given the high surface region of the development pond, protozoan pimples and helminth eggs are likewise eliminated, with sedimentation as the principle mechanism (Verbyla, von Sperling and Ynoussa, 2017; von Sperling, 2007). Sludge accumulation is shallow in maturation ponds. High microbe evacuation efficiencies might be accomplished, contingent upon a few elements: temperature, water-powered maintenance time (the measure of time the fluid stays in the framework - from access to leave), the number of ponds in the arrangement, the presence of puzzles and the profundity of ponds (Verbyla, von Sperling and Ynoussa 2017). Development pond might be utilized in mix with a water store to shape an environmental, self-cleaning water system reservoir, Ecological water basins used for agricultural irrigation (Swim Pond Incorporated, 2011).

2.2. Application and Suitability

Waste adjustment ponds are incredibly productive in their essential goal of eliminating natural waste and, under certain conditions, pathogenic living species. Their plan model has changed almost no over the years (Cincinnati, 2010). Ponds are easy to construct, work and keep up, significant in distant and third-world nations where refined hardware and profoundly talented work are not effectively accessible. Waste adjustment ponds function admirably in practically

all conditions and can treat most sorts of wastewater (von Sperling, 2007). They are especially appropriate for tropical and subtropical nations because the power of the daylight and temperature are vital components of the effectiveness of the evacuation processes (von Sperling, 2007). Ponds are utilized throughout the world. Ponds are the most broadly utilized treatment measure in numerous nations and areas. Hence, they are one of the cycles suggested by WHO for the treatment of wastewater for reuse in farming and hydroponics, particularly in light of their adequacy in eliminating nematodes (worms) and helminth eggs (WHO, 2006). Ponds cannot accomplish high efficiencies in expelling natural waste and, for the most part, have low capacities for eliminating nitrogen and phosphorus. The profluent typically has high groupings of suspended solids due to algal creation in the pond. Subsequently, ponds are not an appropriate innovation in zones where rigid release guidelines exist, except if different post-treatment phases are included (von Sperling, 2016; Morris, 2010). Since ponds require a large area, they may not be common sense near towns where land is costly. Appropriate geology and a reasonable soil structure are also wanted to lessen development costs.

Chapter Three

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This section will cover how the research was carried out to finally come up with the result.

3.1. Conceptual Framework

The call for the rehabilitation of a 49-year-old Unitech sewage pond has a high focus in the release from a past report (Michael, P. S., Fitzpatrick, W. R. and Reid, R., 2017) rather than a low focus at the gushing point contrasted with the admissible base cut-off for substantial metals. These discoveries have set off a further examination to contemplate the impacts of the profluent pond. Michael et al. (2017) expect that macrophytes' senescence contributes back to the pond by adding to high fixation at the emanating pond or the underground and surface stream from nearby enterprises. The critical factor utilized in this investigation is pond type 1. Anaerobic, 2. facultative, and 3. effluent laid correspondingly. At the same time, the needy factors are water, plant and soil tests from every pond inside the investigation locales and control from the impartial site outside the pond site.

3.2. Pond Design and Layout

The first pond (influent or anaerobic pond) is 50 m x 30 m. the second pond is facultative and is 60 m x 66 m. The third pond (aerobic or maturation) is 80 m x 66 m. The ponds are designated P1, P2 and P3, respectively. They have different treatment and design characteristic.

Figure 3: Sewerage pond layout and design. Key: 2a = current design and layout. 2b = suggested design and layout. (Source: Map from Unitech Project Office)

3.3. General Concept

Industrial wastewaters, including sewage, contain organic matter. Discharged untreated wastewater into surface water such as rivers and lakes that contain organic matter may serve as food to other microorganisms living in surface water. Most of these organisms use organic matter for energy, growth and reproduction. Respiration is another vital component in converting organic matter into carbon dioxide and water. Mainly these stable components do not cause water pollution problems, which is called "stabilization" of the organic matter. However, many of these organisms use oxygen in their respiration process, which reduces oxygen concentration in the surface waters causing water pollution problems that directly affect the surface water biota, including fish and other marine life (von Sperling, 2005; von Sperling, 2007).

Waste adjustment ponds imitate these natural behaviours before they occur in the surface water and cause contamination issues because of oxygen utilization. The pond gets wastewater, and, by characteristic cycles like those in the surface waters, complete adjustment of the natural waste inside them as a treatment feature. It is the reason they got the name waste adjustment ponds or waste stabilization ponds (von Sperling, 2007).

3.4. Microorganisms

The responses happen through the joint support of a few microorganisms inside the pond. Human waste is estimated as a biochemical oxygen request (BOD). Body esteems in the pond gushing are lower than in the influent, reflecting the evacuation of natural issues. This pond biome utilizes natural issues from the wastewater as food.

Supplements are changed over to cell material and energy for everyday routine cycles, including propagation and development of experiencing cells. Some of these living cells will be devoured by creatures at higher trophic levels inside the pond. In ponds, the most significant gathering of microorganisms are microbes, which use the greater part of the natural waste from the wastewater and devour oxygen.

Green growth is another fundamental gathering of microorganisms. They do not rely upon the natural material from the influence. Instead, they embrace photosynthesis, in which they produce the natural issue for their utilization and, critically here, they discharge oxygen. The

overabundance of oxygen delivered underpins the breath done by the high-impact life forms in the ponds. Barometrical oxygen is likewise disintegrated into the fluid, which helps with keeping up a high-impact layer on the head of the pond surface.

3.5. Level of Oxygen

The oxygen concentration close to the surface is high and supports the growth of aerobic organisms. Due to low sunlight penetration and reduced photosynthetic activity, those close to the pond bottom cause oxygen concentrations to be low there. The inside the sediments in the bottom layer, there is no oxygen. Here, organic matter is removed by digestion undertaken by anaerobic organisms (von Sperling, 2007).

3.6. Pathogen Removal

Microbes can be proficiently eliminated in squander adjustment ponds. The cycle generally depends on the development pond for evacuation of microbes, albeit some expulsion additionally happens in different ponds of the framework. The higher the quantity of pond in the arrangement, the more productive the microorganism expulsion. The expulsion of pathogenic microorganisms and infections happens fundamentally by inactivation. Microorganisms are inactivated because of an unpredictable communication of instruments that include pH (the pH esteem in a pond is high as a result of algal photosynthesis), temperature, bright radiation present in the daylight that arrives at the lake surface and photooxidative responses exploiting high disintegrated oxygen concentrations (Weaver, Webber, Karki, Thomas, Mackenzie, Lin, Inglis and Williamson, 2016; Verbyla *et al.*, 2017).

Protozoan microorganisms are available in the wastewater as pimples or oocysts. Helminths (worms) are available as eggs. The protozoan and helminth microorganisms can be eliminated by the component of sedimentation (Verbyla *et al.*, 2017). Very high evacuation efficiencies might be accomplished, mainly if influential ponds are essential for the treatment framework. All things considered, the last effluent pond might be in accordance with World Health Organization rules for inundating with treated wastewater (or "recovered water") (WHO, 2006). However, ooze (silt) from the pond might be intensely debased with helminth eggs, which may endure even following quite a while of putting away the slope within the pond (Oakley, 2005).

3.7. Activity and Maintenance

As for support, the assignments performed by the operational staff are exceptionally straightforward and do not need unique abilities. Also, there is no energy utilization for air circulation, no need for hefty hardware support, regular slope evacuation, or ooze treatment and removal. Ponds require almost no upkeep since no weighty electric or mechanical hardware requires consideration. The primary routine upkeep required is the fundamental treatment (cleaning of screens and expulsion of solids), routine checking of lines, weirs and other pressure-driven structures, and evacuation of undesirable vegetation development in ponds (von Sperling, 2005; von Sperling, 2007).

3.8. Removal of Sludge

Sludge collected inside the pond should be eliminated distinctly at yearly intervals. It is a significant bit of leeway in the framework. In any case, when expulsion is essential, it is typically a costly and work escalated activity. Removing is more incessant in anaerobic ponds (at regular intervals) due to their littler volume and lower ability to store the ooze contrasted and facultative pond. In the facultative pond, muck removal might be fundamental just in stretches around 15 to 25 years. In development ponds, sludge is very low (von Sperling, 2007). Sludge or slime expulsion, likewise called desludging, might be done in two important ways: (i) interfering with the activity of the pond for desludging or (ii) keeping the lake in activity while desludging (von Sperling, 2007). In the main case, the influent wastewater to the pond to be de-sludged is close. A while later, the pond is depleted, and the base sludge is left for open drying for half a month. During this period, the wastewater to be dealt with should be redirected to different ponds in the framework. After the slime has dried, its evacuation might be done physically or precisely utilizing work vehicles or mechanical scrubbers. In the other option, when the pond is left in activity during desludging, the eliminated muck will be wet and require further drying. It is outside the pond. Sludge evacuation can be by attractions and siphoning utilizing vacuum trucks (just for little lakes), digging, siphoning from a pontoon or including other mechanical gear. In either case, the measure of sludge to be taken out is exceptionally high, considering its collection over a time of years. This cycle is arduous, costly and requires cautious planning (von Sperling, 2007).

3.9. Costs Analysis

In choosing a wastewater treatment measure, other than the specialized perspectives pertinent to every other option, additionally, cost factors assume a significant job. The last can be essentially isolated into (i) development expenses and (ii) activity and upkeep costs. Squander adjustment ponds are generally viewed as a modest option as far as development costs. Nonetheless, the final costs will depend on the size of ponds, the presence of development ponds in the process design, geography, soil conditions, groundwater level and land cost (von Sperling, 2007). Since every component is site-explicit, it is hard to sum up, general development costs. As a rule, these will be lower contrasted and other wastewater treatment alternatives (Arthur, 1983; von Sperling, 2005). Depending on the particular circumstance of the territory, development expenses can increment and level up with different innovations. Squander adjustment ponds are one of the least expensive wastewater treatment measures regarding activity and maintenance (von Sperling, 2007).

3.10. Experimental Design and Field Sampling

The survey's focus was to determine potential plant species widely influential in all ponds. Apart from that, soil & sludge were tested to identify present and future scenarios of the ponds. Literature has pointed out that some plants are ideal for phytoremediation of heavy metals such as arsenic, copper, chromium and cadmium in open sewage ponds (Pilon-Smith, 2005). Having this foundation on the viewpoint, purposive design and grab sampling technique were adopted in sampling triplicate soil, water and plant samples from all the ponds. The data bestowed are derived from a single sampling carried out in June 2020. The first pond (influent pond) was modelled 1 m away from each side of the inlet, outlet passage and the two sides.

Identically, in the second pond, representatives were modelled right in the centre of each four sides. Representatives of the third pond (effluent pond) were modelled 1 m from the four sides. Biological treatment occurred at the effluent pond (Third pond) before being discharged into the environment. The matured leaf samples of the most dominant plant were collected in all three ponds. Like 1 kg, soil samples were collected 0.5 m away from the sampling point in all three ponds.

Similarly, 250 mL water samples were collected near where plant leaves were sampled. Samples were collected from, Control, pond 1, pond 2 and pond 3. Water, plants and soil

samples were collected in triplicate from all sites. Water samples were taken straight to the laboratory, while plant samples were cut and dried in an oven at 40 °C for 72 hours before grinding for further testing. Soil samples were dried using open air for 7 days before sieving using 35 mesh sieves and finally 270 mesh sieves for further testing. A total of 16 soil samples, 16 water samples and 20 plant samples were collected, prepared and tested. Samples were tested at the Unitech Analytical lab. Part of the water samples was transferred to NAL for Biological Oxidation Demand (BOD) test. The second focus of the survey was to determine the present and future scenarios of the three ponds laid parallel to each other. In this case, sludge and plant samples were not tested out due to time limitations. A total of twelve dominant plant samples were collected and tested, which identified their potential for concentration uptake. All data from the sites were grouped as RW- control sites at Raunwara (Snack Bar), P1, P2 and P3, respectively for the three ponds.

3.11. Laboratory and Statistical Data Analysis

Sampling is based on the investigation of (Al- Musharafi, S. K., Mahmoud, I., and Al-Bahry, S., 2013), and all samples were composited and examination done at the University Analytical research facility (UASL) as per strategies (APHA, 1998). The leaves tested were dried at 40 °C for 72 hours, and samples of 0.5 g each were placed in polymer containers. These were treated with 0.5 mL of hydrofluoric acid and 4 mL of concentrated nitric acid and warmed in the microwave for 40 minutes. These were weakened to 100 mL with milli-Q water to give the final concentration of 1 g.L⁻¹ (Moor et al., 2011). These samples were sifted and examined for As, Cd, Cu and Cr utilizing the (ICP-OES) type Pekin Elmer 3300 DV ICP (USA). Blank and certified reference solutions were used as control.

Similarly, the BOD test was carried out at NATSL at the Papua New Guinea University of Technology. Newly gathered water samples from the ponds were taken to the lab with a filled BOD bottle without air bubbles. Added 2 mL of manganese sulphate to the BOD bottle cautiously by embedding the pipette beneath the outside water to avoid the development of air bubbles. Added 2 mL of soluble base iodide-azide reagent similarly, closed the container, and blended the example by transforming commonly. An earthy cloud will show up in the arrangement as a pointer to the presence of oxygen. Permitted the earthy coloured hasten to settle out to the base. At that point, 2 mL of concentrated H₂SO₄ was added cautiously without shaping air rises with shut container blended the arrangement disintegrated the hasten. The

BOD vessels and the samples were kept for 5 days (BOD₅). After dilution, titrate 50 mL of the sample with 0.025 N sodium thiosulphate to a light-yellow colour. Then 2 ml of the starch indicator was added to the sample to give a blue colour. The titration was continued until the solution became colourless. The amount of oxygen is equal to the mL of titrant utilized. The method employed at NATSL was NAL/WL31.

Table 1. Minimum permissible levels (MPL) of the selected heavy metals in drinking water, irrigation, plants and soil (FAO, 1985; FAO, 1989; WHO, 1996).

Heavy Metal	Minimum Permissible Level			
	(Units are in parts per million mass/volume or mass per mass.)			
	Drinking	Irrigation	Plants	Soil
Cadmium	0.003	0.02	0.2	0.8
Copper	2.00	10	10	36
Arsenic	0.05	2	0.5	85
Chromium	0.01	0.6	1	50

Table.2 Permissible limits for metals (Everett Wilson and Carl Solomon 7/95)

Metal	Sample Matrix							
	Primary Drinking Water Standard (MCL) mg/L	Secondary Drinking Water Standard mg/L	Hazardous Waste Screening Criteria (TCLP) mg/kg	TCLP Hazardous Waste Limit mg/L	Common Range in Soils mg/kg	Livestock Water Quality mg/L	Surface Water Quality mg/L	Land Application of Sewerage Sludge ppm
Arsenic	0.05	–	100	5	1–50; 770664	0.5	0.4	75
Cadmium	0.005	–	20	1	0.01–0.70	0.5	0.2	85
Chromium	0.10	–	100	5	1–1,000; 5–3,000	1	0.5	3,000
Copper	1.39	1	–	–	2–100	0.5	1	4,300

The MPLs of water, plant and soil samples are in mas per mass (FAO, 1985) and mg.kg-1 (WHO, 1996), respectively. The treatment average was obtained by taking the mean of the three replicates. To compare the treatment means, the significance difference ($p < 0.05$) between the treatment means of the samples was determined by one-sample T-test using Statistical Package for the Social Science (SPSS).

Chapter Four

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Most of the results in this section consist of tables, graphs and field surveys, laboratory testing and further SPSS software analysis. Specifically, a T-test was carried out to come up with the graphs and tables. All results for the four sites where data was collected are represented in graphs and tables below.

Table: 3 One-Sample Test result for plant species against the sites, control (0) Pond 1 (1), Pond 2 (2) and pond 3 (3) for plant samples as indicated on the table in the metal column.

Metal (mg/L)	Test Value = 0.05					
	t	df	Sig. (2 tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of Difference	
					Lower	Upper
Arsenic (0)	-61.800	7	0.000	-0.46625	-0.4841	-0.4484
Cadmium (0)	-36.222	7	0.000	0-.45375	-0.4834	-0.4241
Copper (0)	10.960	7	0.000	5.32875	4.1791	6.4784
Chromium (0)	0.328	7	0.753	0.03375	-0.2098	0.2773
Arsenic (1)	1.713	3	0.185	0.17500	-0.1502	0.5002
Cadmium (1)	1.425	3	0.249	0.24500	-0.3023	0.7923
Copper (1)	47.179	3	0.000	6.77250	6.3157	7.2293
Chromium (1)	0.000	3	1.000	0.00000	-0.4944	0.4944
Arsenic (2)	1.944	3	0.147	0.22750	-0.1449	0.5999
Cadmium (2)	12.677	3	0.001	0.37500	0.2809	0.4691
Copper (2)	14.273	3	0.001	8.53250	6.6300	10.4350
Chromium (2)	16.432	3	0.000	0.45000	-0.3628	0.5372

Arsenic	(3)	16.769	3	0.000	0.52750	0.4274	0.6276
Cadmium	(3)	0.919	3	0.426	0.10750	-0.2646	0.4796
Copper	(3)	32.899	3	0.000	10.75250	9.7124	11.7926
Chromium	(3)	1.975	3	0.143	4.94250	-3.0202	12.9052

4.1. Dominant Weeds Species in Study Area

Some of the most dominant weed species or water plants identified and collected for further testing are:

Oxynopus compressus, *Megathyrus maximus*, *Amaranthus spinosus*, *Eleusine indica*, *Cynodon dactylions*, *Ipomea aquatica*, *Agerantum conyzoides*, *Euphorbia heterophylla*, *Sida acuta* and *Eichornia crassipes*. As per the Tables 3 and 4; and graphs 1, 2 and 3 below showing strong indication that the above plants heavily absorb Cu compared to As, Cd and Cr. (See Appendix for individual species list).

Table 4 showing one sample test for plants species in sites

Metal (mg/L)	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Standard Error on Mean
Arsenic (0)	8	0.0338	0.02134	0.00754
Cadmium (0)	8	0.0463	0.03543	0.01253
Copper (0)	8	5.8288	1.37518	0.48620
Chromium (0)	8	0.5338	0.29130	0.10299
Arsenic (1)	4	0.6750	0.20437	0.10218
Cadmium (1)	4	0.7450	0.34395	0.17197
Copper (1)	4	7.2725	0.28710	0.14355
Chromium (1)	4	0.5000	0.31070	0.15535
Arsenic (2)	4	0.7275	0.23400	0.11700
Cadmium (2)	4	0.8750	0.05916	0.02958
Copper (2)	4	9.0325	1.19564	0.59782
Chromium (2)	4	0.9500	0.05477	0.02739
Arsenic (3)	4	1.0275	0.06292	0.03146
Cadmium (3)	4	0.6075	0.23386	0.11693
Copper (3)	4	11.2525	0.65368	0.32684
Chromium (3)	4	5.4425	5.00414	2.50207

Graph 1 showing weeds (plants) species in sites and its concentration characteristic

4.2. Test Results for Water Hyacinth in Ponds

Table: 5 one sample T – test

Metal	N	Mean (mg/L)	Standard Deviation	Standard Error on Mean
Arsenic	3	1.7100	0.25239	0.14572
Cadmium	3	0.8933	0.01528	0.00882
Copper	3	14.4667	1.00167	0.57831
Chromium	3	0.7233	0.07024	0.04055

Table: 6 one sample T – test

Metal (mg/L)	Test Value = 0.05					
	<i>t</i>	df	Sig. (2 tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of Difference	
					Lower	Upper
Arsenic	8.304	2	0.014	1.21000	0.5830	1.8370
Cadmium	44.600	2	0.001	0.39333	0.3554	0.4313
Copper	24.151	2	0.002	13.96667	11.4784	16.4549
Chromium	5.507	2	0.031	0.22333	0.0489	0.3978

Graph 2 showing mean, standard deviation and standard error mean for concentration in ponds against the water hyacinth in pond 1, 2 and 3.

Graph: 3 showing the concentration distribution of water hyacinth in ponds

4.3. Results for Soil Samples

Table 7 Overall summary of soil sample test in all sites

Metal (mg/L)	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Standard Error on Mean
Arsenic (0)	4	0.1500	0.05477	0.02739
Cadmium (0)	4	0.3750	0.10847	0.05424
Copper(0)	4	143.2000	17.74768	8.87384
Chromium (0)	4	0.2950	0.09950	0.04975
Arsenic (1)	4	0.4200	0.09832	0.04916
Cadmium (1)	4	0.4150	0.12871	0.06436
Copper(1)	4	149.7800	2.44900	1.22450

Chromium	(1)	4	0.3150	0.06658	0.03329
Arsenic	(2)	4	0.4950	0.03512	0.01756
Cadmium	(2)	4	0.5100	0.04243	0.02121
Copper(2)		4	164.1500	13.18699	6.59349
Chromium	(2)	4	0.5075	0.04856	0.02428
Arsenic	(3)	4	0.5675	0.06752	0.03376
Cadmium	(3)	4	0.5475	0.02754	0.01377
Copper(3)		4	178.9950	13.63459	6.81729
Chromium	(3)	4	1.0075	0.03500	0.01750

Graph 4 showing distribution of heavy metals in soils compared to sites

Table 8 one sample T test for soil in all sites

Metal (mg/L)	Test Value = 0.05					
	<i>t</i>	df	Sig. (2 tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of Difference	
					Lower	Upper
Arsenic (0)	-12.780	3	0.001	-0.35000	-0.4372	-0.2628
Cadmium (0)	-2.305	3	0.105	-0.12500	-0.2976	0.0476
Copper (0)	16.081	3	0.001	142.70000	114.4595	170.9405
Chromium (0)	-4.121	3	0.026	-0.20500	-0.3633	-0.0467
Arsenic (1)	-1.627	3	0.202	-0.08000	-0.2364	0.0764
Cadmium (1)	-1.321	3	0.278	-0.08500	-0.2898	0.1198
Copper (1)	121.911	3	0.000	149.28000	145.3831	153.1769
Chromium (1)	-5.557	3	0.011	-0.18500	-0.2909	-0.0791
Arsenic (2)	-0.285	3	0.794	-0.00500	-0.0609	0.0509
Cadmium (2)	0.471	3	0.670	0.01000	-0.0575	0.0775
Copper (2)	24.820	3	0.000	163.65000	142.6666	184.6334
Chromium (2)	0.309	3	0.778	0.00750	-0.0698	0.0848
Arsenic (3)	2.000	3	0.139	0.06750	-0.0399	0.1749
Cadmium (3)	3.450	3	0.041	0.04750	0.0037	0.0913
Copper (3)	26.183	3	0.000	178.49500	156.7993	200.1907
Chromium (3)	29.000	3	0.000	0.50750	0.4518	0.5632

4.4. Average BOD Values

Graph 5 showing average biological oxidation demand (BOD) in mg/L against the sites.

Table 9 One sample statistic test for water samples in all sites

Metal (mg/L)	Test Value = 0.05					
	<i>t</i>	df	Sig. (2 tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of Difference	
					Lower	Upper
Arsenic (0)	-12.780	3	0.001	-0.35000	-0.4372	-0.2628
Cadmium (0)	-2.305	3	0.105	-0.12500	-0.2976	0.0476
Copper (0)	16.081	3	0.001	142.70000	114.4595	170.9405
Chromium (0)	-4.121	3	0.026	-0.20500	-0.3633	-0.0467
Arsenic (1)	-1.627	3	0.202	-0.08000	-0.2364	0.0764
Cadmium (1)	-1.321	3	0.278	-0.08500	-0.2898	0.1198
Copper (1)	121.911	3	0.000	149.28000	145.3831	153.1769

Chromium	(1)	-5.557	3	0.011	-0.18500	-0.2909	-0.0791
Arsenic	(2)	-0.285	3	0.794	-0.00500	-0.0609	0.0509
Cadmium	(2)	0.471	3	0.670	0.01000	-0.0575	0.0775
Copper	(2)	24.820	3	0.000	163.65000	142.6666	184.6334
Chromium	(2)	0.309	3	0.778	0.00750	-0.0698	0.0848
Arsenic	(3)	2.000	3	0.139	0.06750	-0.0399	0.1749
Cadmium	(3)	3.450	3	0.041	0.04750	0.0037	0.0913
Copper	(3)	26.183	3	0.000	178.49500	156.7993	200.1907
Chromium	(3)	29.000	3	0.000	0.50750	0.4518	0.5632

4.5. Heavy Metals in Water

Graph 6 showing water sample result in all sites

Table: 10 one sample T – Test Summary result for all sites samples

Metal (mg/L)	Test Value = 0.05					
	<i>t</i>	df	Sig. (2 tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of Difference	
					Lower	Upper
Arsenic (0)	-100.544	23	0.000	-0.47750	-0.4873	-0.4677
Cadmium (0)	-57.756	23	0.000	-0.45458	-0.4709	-0.4383
Copper (0)	5.534	23	0.000	3.38917	2.1222	4.6561
Chromium (0)	-2.007	23	0.057	-0.13792	-0.2801	0.0042
Arsenic (1)	-1.748	15	0.101*	-0.16250	-0.3606	0.0356
Cadmium (1)	-1.111	15	0.284*	-0.12125	-0.3538	0.1113
Copper (1)	3.440	15	0.004*	3.18813	1.2128	5.1635
Chromium (1)	-2.544	15	0.022*	-0.17188	-0.3159	-0.0279
Arsenic (2)	-.131	11	0.898	-0.01500	-0.2677	0.2377
Cadmium (2)	.719	11	0.487*	0.08833	-0.1821	0.3588
Copper (2)	4.322	11	0.001*	5.57000	2.7333	8.4067
Chromium (2)	1.686	11	0.120*	0.18917	-0.0578	0.4361
Arsenic (3)	.914	12	0.039*	0.13231	-0.1833	0.4479
Cadmium (3)	-1.284	12	0.023*	-0.12308	-0.3320	0.0858
Copper (3)	4.108	12	0.001*	6.46000	3.0335	9.8865
Chromium (3)	2.320	12	0.039*	2.87385	0.1754	5.5723

4.6. Discussion

The heavy metals concentration in the control site (Raunwara) were below the MPLs except for Cu in pond 1, 2 and 3 for a plant, soil and water samples, as indicated on graph 1, 2, 3 and decreases in graph 6 with a slight variation of Cr increases and decreases in effluent ponds. Compared to the concentration in the samples, the concentration in the wastewater, plants and soil has a common relationship of very high concentration of Cu and Cr were found in the sample in pond three, indicated in graphs 1 – 4. The P-value as = 0.379ml/L, Cd- 0.223mg/L, Cu-0.001mg/l and Cr-0.039. Compared to these, the concentration in the control site was much

lower, ranging from As, Cd, and Cu-0.00mg/L while Cr – 0.057mg/L. Similarly, the heavy metals concentration in all samples collected in the ponds varied. An asterisk (*) indicates a significant difference ($P < 0.05$) between the groups (RW, P1, P2 and P3 treatment and control). The concentration of heavy metals in the control pond was zero compared to Cr with 0.057mg/L. In pond 1 the concentration of As-0.101mg/L, Cd-0.284mg/L was much lower than Cu-0.004mg/L, Cr-0.022mg/L. Pond 1 and 2 had a low concentration of As, Cd and Cr, while there was a high concentration of Cu in the sites, as shown on graphs 1-4. However, in pond 3, the concentration for As, Cd and Cu were low, and Cr was high with a P-value < 0.05 , as shown in table 10. The sig. (2 tailed) value is less than 0.05. Because of this, I concluded that there is a statistically significant difference between P1, P2 & P3. The smaller the p-value of As =0.039m, Cd=0.023mg/L, Cu=0.010mg/L, Cr=0.039mg/L indicated stronger evidence that should reject the null hypothesis. A p-value less than 0.05 (typically ≤ 0.05) is statistically significant. It indicated strong evidence against the null hypothesis, as there is less than a 5% probability that the null is correct and the results are random.

Contrasted with the MPLs of different variables (Table 1), the concentration of the apparent multitude of heavy metals surpassed the standard MPLS of water, plants, and even soil. The overall pattern fluctuated in the concentration in the influent (pond 1) to the effluent (pond 3) in the wastewater framework. The immediate release from the domestic resident into the influent pond was not sampled for analysis due to the hefty presence of faeces and odour. In this pond, there was an increasing concentration of substantial metals in wastewater and plant leaves, yet the focus was higher on leaves and soil than on wastewater. The higher test result indicates that As, Cd, Cu, and Cr in leaves demonstrated that macrophytes had the option to eliminate most of the metals from the wastewater (Graph 2). Lia and Chang (2004) carried out a similar study and reported that bioaccumulation in heavy metals by plants in constructed wetlands is essential compared to this study.

Furthermore, other findings prove that water plants are capable of heavy metal uptake and are limited to laboratory or glasshouse conditions (Hussain, S. T., Mohmood, T. and Malik, S. A (2010), (Sreelekha, N., Subramanyam, K., Reddy, D. A., Murali, G., Varma, K. R., & Vijayalakshmi, R. P.,2016). The change in heavy metal in the second pond showed a similar trend as in the first pond, as shown in summary Tables 3-10 and Graphs 1-4. These had shown that high quantities of metals were present in the wastewater, plants and soil samples collected and tested. The most critical pond is the third pond, where effluent is discharged into the surrounding environment. In this pond, there was high availability of Cd, Cu and Cr, as shown

in Graph 6, compared to As in the wastewater. In the plant leaves and soil, a high amount of Cu was present, indicating a fair amount of these metals are available in the pond wastewater and likely to be disposed into the nearby environment. Graph 5 for BOD results showed a clear relationship with the concentration in each pond as identified. The higher the concentration, the lower the BOD and vice versa compared with Graph 6.

A fascinating finding is a fluctuation in metal concentration in every pond. The investigation demonstrated an expanding concentration of heavy metals in P1 and P2 and decreased at P3 (effluent), as shown in Graph 6. In both water, plant and soil, Table 10, Graphs 1–4 show that heavy metals that reach the ponds are taken up by the roots of plants in the ponds and bioaccumulated in the leaves, Michael *et al.* (2011) was 91 % of Cr removal was reported. The most likely motivation behind why the fixation is high in the effluent pond as distinguished is the pool of routine upkeep by methods for eliminating undesirable weeds and dead plants in the lakes. The previous examination revealed that marshland plants develop and senesce, and turnover of the natural waste from them ends up once more into wastewater. Deterioration of these plants delivers the substantial metals bioaccumulation back into the wastewater framework could be the most plausible explanation for a high measure of heavy metals still accessible in the wastewater Michael *et al.* (2011). High accessibility is a significant worry as it presents a serious danger to portability and can bring about ecological contamination.

In numerous sewage frameworks, the fixation in the gushing pond is relied upon to be less contrasted with the discoveries. The outcome in tables 8.9 and 10 indicated that it has expanded. That could be the surface stream's or underground leachate's purpose (Roldan, 2002). Phytoremediation by *E. crassipe*, as appeared in Table 6 and Graph 1, showed a decrease in the odds of heavy metals' versatility in the climate (Roldan, 2002). The proof of an expanding focus, even in small amounts, may include legitimate administration to diminish the high odds of heavy metal collection (Madyiwa, S., Chimbari, M., Nyamangara, J., and Bangira, C., 2002). announced that the accessibility of heavy metals is a significant worry as bioaccumulation is hindering a significant accepting biological system and public ecological wellbeing.

The innovation used to oversee sewage wastewater relies on the people's way of life and the climatic condition of sewage. People's way of life influences the characteristics and natural cycles related to phytoremediation that happen to treat water (Aizari, H. A., Lebkiri, A., Fadliz, M., and Albaseer, S. S., 2017). Wastewater was reused in agribusiness, and the training has benefits (Naddafi, K., Jaafarzadeh, N., Mokhtari, M., Zakizadeh, B. and Sakian, M. R., 2005).

In weak economies, this choice is not thought of and keeps on raising the worry that substantial metal accessibility and portability from sewage ponds are a wellbeing danger (Nadafi *et al.*, 2005). One investigation indicated the accessibility of sewage ponds in the tropic, yet the exhibition is low because of the absence of appropriate management (Abdel-Raouf, N., Al-Homaidan, A. A., and Ibraheem, I. B M., 2012). Appropriate management, for example, ordinary support, helps diminish the high accessibility of suspended solids, natural issues, and supplements which are an extra source of contamination (Lim, S., Chu, W., and Pang, S., 2010).

Under the turnover of the natural waste and arrival of the heavy metal once more into the wastewater, removing plants macrophytes from the ponds before senescence and death is one significant choice accessible to help diminish the availability in the ponds. The plants eliminated from the lakes can be dried, burnt, and remains covered to limit air contamination, or the entire plants eliminated from ponds can be permitted to dry out and utilized as organic matter. The standard support would be with the end goal that a great populace, or the entire plant material that is covering the pond, be eliminated. Young shoots stay in the pond and keep developing, ideally developing enough to a high aggregate grouping of substantial metals, which will be eliminated comparatively. Studies have demonstrated the division of metal-immersed green growth as a monetary strategy for eliminating substantial metals in ponds (Kiran, B., Kaushik, A. and Kaushik, C. P ., 2007, Bhat, S., V. Melo, J. S., Chaugule, B. B. and Souza, S. F. D., 2008; Pandi, M., Shashirekha, V. and Swamy, M., 2009).

By looking at the result in graphs 1- 4, Copper (Cu) is a very high and fundamental micronutrient in water, soils and leaves samples collected apart from As, Cr and Cd. These showed that it is vital in many plant cycles, for example, breath, photosynthesis, oxidative pressure, nitrogen, and carbon digestion, chemical perception, and cell divider combination (Pilon, M, Abdel-Ghany S. E., Cohu C M, Gogolin K A, Ye, H, 2006; Hansch & Mendel, 2009). Copper insufficiency in plants can prompt growth hindrances such as yellowing of young leaves and hinder growth (Klaumann, S., Nickolaus, S. D., Fürst, S. H., Starck, S., Schneider, S., Ekkehard Neuhaus, H., & Trentmann, O, 2011). Cu is also vital for fruitfulness and lessens the development rate, seed-setting rate, and yield (Huang, X. Y., Deng, F. L., Yamaji, N., Pinson, S. R. M., Fujii-Kashino, M., Danku, J. Douglas, A., Guerinot, M. L., Salt, D. E., Ma. J. F, 2016). Cu is a significant part of human wellbeing (Collins & Klevay, 2011; Gulec & Collins, 2014). Insufficiency of Cu may cause iron deficiency and immune imperfections (Collins & Klevay, 2011). As of now, over two billion+ individuals experienced the ill effects of micronutrient insufficiencies, for example, Cu, iron (Fe), and zinc (Zn) (White

& Broadley, 2009). In addition, unreasonable Cu is poisonous to plants (Abdel-Ghany, S. E., Müller-Moulé, P., Niyogi, K. K., Pilon, M., & Shikanai, T, 2005; Andrés-Colás, N., Sancenón, V., Rodríguez-Navarro, S., Mayo, S., Thiele, D. J., Ecker, J. R., and Peñarrubia, L, 2006) and offers to ascend plant root development hindrance, biomass decrease, and plant putrefaction (Navari-Izzo, F., Quartacci, M. F., Argilla, A., & Baker, A. J. M, 2006; Lequeux, H., Hermans, C., Lutts, S., & Verbruggen, N., 2010; Huang et al., 2016). Cu toxicity can yellow leaves and decrease the photosynthetic pace of plants (Alaoui-Sossé et al., 2004; Bernal, G., & Sáez-Santiago, E., 2006). Heavy Cu toxicity additionally diminishes iron uptake by plants (Alaoui-Sossé et al., 2004), and thylakoid layers in chloroplasts are likewise significant focuses of Cu harmfulness (Bernal et al., 2004).

Removal of the plants and sentiments around them would bring about surface blending. Consequently, high-impact decay and odour, yet the advantage of the standard support, mainly to help lessen heavy metal accessibility of toxins, coincide with live plants (Rono, 2018). Expulsion of plant macrophytes would help diminish strongly connected to sentiments around live plants, further decreasing the substantial metals in the pond framework (Rezania, S., Ponraj, M., Din, M. D., Chelliapan, S. and Sairan, D. Md., 2016). Identified wetland plant species, for example, (*Eichhornia crassipe*) (See appendices, identified plants species table) use parenchymatous tissue to take in oxygen and oxygenate the rhizosphere significantly under anaerobic condition (Michael et al., 2017; Michael and Reid, 2018; Michael, 2018). In the sewage framework, the presence of dominant plant macrophytes as identified changed physiological highlights, for example, *O. compressus*, *M. maximus*, *A. spinosus*, *E. indica*, *C. dactylions*, *I. aquatica*, *A. conyzoides*, *E. heterophylla*, *S. acuta* and *Eichhornia crassipe*, particularly under tropical conditions and is a favourable position to treat home-grown waste by phytoremediation and tissue collection. These sorts of plants help control biochemical and biophysical measures. It is significant for treating sewage using characteristic and organic methods (Anushee, 2005). The guideline of the cycle is significant for microbial concentration in sewage ponds that depend on supplement stacking, temperature, pH, and daylight to rhizomadiate heavy metal. Much of the time, anaerobic decay neutralizes these and prompts the arrival of CO₂, adding to the greenhouse gas emission. The deterioration under low O₂ further prompts a decreased response raising the pH to level up with essential organisms. It therefore shows to have a regular maintenance. It sufficiently reduces and mixes the wastewater in the sewage ponds despite the community disadvantage of odour.

Chapter Five

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The phytoremediation of substantial metals by existing plants is ineffective. The deterioration of dead plant matter appears to deliver the hefty metals bioaccumulation back into the wastewater framework, making them promptly accessible for conceivable versatility in the environment. Removal of plants macrophyte regularly would help diminish the accessibility and versatility in the emanating and prevent environmental contamination. These outcomes have suggested managing wastewater sewage framework overwhelmed by plant macrophytes, particularly under moist marsh tropical climatic conditions. There were some limitations encountered in sampling water, plants and soil due to funding issues which some objectives of the study were not answered. The Biochemical oxygen demand (BOD) and microorganisms in the ponds are very high. It can cause water-related diseases such as typhoid, paratyphoid, bacillary dysentery, gastroenteritis, and cholera. The higher BOD in the ponds means the sewerage system is not functioning well and might cause diseases to the general public. The BOD is the oxygen required for microbial decomposition of a unit mass of organic remains, in which the degree of water impurity due to organic matter is measured in terms of BOD. A higher BOD of a pond or water source indicates that water is highly polluted and requires more oxygen. Thus demanding more species to feed on, signifying a lower water quality. The low BOD, on the other hand, means less oxygen is being removed from the water, so water is generally purer. Demand for further study to look into the ponds 1, 2, 3 and nearby stream or water sources to make BOD count and relate them to water-prone diseases is a future gap researcher may look into.

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APPENDIX

Soil sample data

UNITECH ANALYTICAL SERVICES LABORATORY
 Department of Agriculture
 PNG University of Technology
CHEMICAL ANALYSIS REPORT - SOIL

Private Mail Bag
 UE 411, Morobe Province
 Tel: +675 473 4451

CLIENT: Mr Charles Farnock
 Post Graduate Student
 C/- Department of Civil Engineering
 PWS, PNGUOT

ATTN: Dr Betasolo

JOB ID: J06-20
DATE: 8 Sep 2020

ORDER NO: LR-005

Page 1 of 1

LAB No.	SAMPLE ID	CLIENT ID	TEST		Total Cu	Total Cr
			UNITS	METHOD		
20120	Round Wara Sample #1 Site #1 Outer		Total As mg/L	Total Cd mg/L	Total Cu mg/L	Total Cr mg/L
20220	Round Wara Sample#2, Smeaz, Centre (R/S)		HNO3 ICP-OES	HNO3 ICP-OES	HNO3 ICP-OES	HNO3 ICP-OES
20320	Round Wara Sample #3 Site #3 Centre (L/S)		0.23	0.53	134.60	0.42
20420	Round Wara Sample #4 Site #4 Inlet		0.17	0.33	152.30	0.17
20620	Pond # 1 Site 1 Sample 1		0.14	0.36	162.80	0.31
20720	Pond # 1 Site 1 Sample 2		0.11	0.28	123.10	0.18
20820	Pond # 1 Site 1 Sample 3		0.28	0.53	152.92	0.31
20920	Pond # 1 Site 1 Sample 4		0.45	0.33	148.90	0.25
21020	Pond # 2 Site 2 Sample 1		0.44	0.28	147.10	0.15
21120	Pond # 2 Site 2 Sample 2		0.51	0.52	150.20	0.41
21220	Pond # 2 Site 2 Sample 3		0.53	0.54	162.80	0.52
21320	Pond # 2 Site 2 Sample 4		0.46	0.46	155.70	0.48
21420	Pond #3 Site 3 Sample 1		0.47	0.49	154.90	0.46
21520	Pond #3 Site 3 Sample 2		0.52	0.55	183.20	0.57
	Pond #3 Site 3 Sample 3		0.61	0.58	191.76	1.02
	Pond #3 Site 3 Sample 4		0.55	0.52	168.80	0.99
	Pond #3 Site 3 Sample 5		0.48	0.53	185.72	0.97

Checked By:
 AGRICULTURE DEPARTMENT
 PAPUA NEW GUINEA
 UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY
 PWS
 LAE
 PAPUA NEW GUINEA

Approved By:
 AGRICULTURE DEPARTMENT
 PAPUA NEW GUINEA
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Date: 08/09/20

Biological oxidation demand data

NAL NATIONAL ANALYSIS LABORATORY **UNITECH DEVELOPMENT & CONSULTANCY Pty Ltd**
 BOX 79
 UNITECH PO ,LAE
 PAPUA NEW GUINEA
 FAX: (675) 473 4578
 FAX: (675) 475 7667
 TEL: (675) 473 4571

Client: **Civil Engineering Dept.
 Unitech
 Lae
 Morobe, Papua New Guinea**

Job: **374/020**

Clients Ref: **Charles Feriwok**

Aug 10, 2020
 Page 1 of 1

 P.N.G.L.A.S Signatory

For the 10 samples analysed "as received" by this laboratory on Aug 3, 2020 the following is supplied:

Client Sample Label	NAL Ref	Analysis	Analysis Results	Method
Site# 1 Round wana Sample #1 outlet 22.07.2020	1583/20	BOD, 5 day	8.9 mg/L	NAL/WL31 ✓
Site# 1 Pond #1 Sample #3 28.07.2020	1584/20	BOD, 5 day	62 mg/L	NAL/WL31 ✓
Site# 1 Pond #1 Sample #1 Inlet 28.07.2020	1585/20	BOD, 5 day	219 mg/L	NAL/WL31 ✓
Site# 1 Pond #1 Main inlet 28.07.2020	1586/20	BOD, 5 day	16 mg/L	NAL/WL31 ✓
Site# 2 Pond #2 Sample #1 28.07.2020	1587/20	BOD, 5 day	51 mg/L	NAL/WL31 ✓
Site# 2 Pond #2 Sample #3 28.07.2020	1588/20	BOD, 5 day	48 mg/L	NAL/WL31 ✓
Site# 3 Pond #3 Sample #3 28.07.2020	1589/20	BOD, 5 day	70 mg/L	NAL/WL31 ✓
Site# 3 Pond#3 sample#1 28.07.2020	1590/20	BOD, 5 day	52 mg/L	NAL/WL31 ✓
Site# 3 Pond #3 Main outlet 28.07.2020	1591/20	BOD, 5 day	7.3 mg/L	NAL/WL31 ✓
Site# 4 Round wana Sample #6 Inlet 22.07.2020	1592/20	BOD, 5 day	7.0 mg/L	NAL/WL31 ✓

As per the Code of Minimum Standards a fee which is not assessed under P.N.G.L.A.S. accreditation. No annotation in the Certificate shall indicate that P.N.G.L.A.S. accreditation does not cover performance of this analysis. This annotation shall only be retrofitted in its entirety to

Weeds or Plants samples data

UNITECH ANALYTICAL SERVICES LABORATORY

Department of Agriculture
 PNG University of Technology

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CHEMICAL ANALYSIS REPORT

LAB No.	SAMPLE ID	TEST UNITS	Tot.Az		Tot.Cd		Tot.Cr	
			mg/L	mg/L	mg/L	mg/L	mg/L	mg/L
		METHOD	HOOA	HOOA	HOOA	HOOA	HOOA	HOOA
		BY	ICP/OES	ICP/OES	ICP/OES	ICP/OES	ICP/OES	ICP/OES
21600	Pond # 2 Site 2 Sample 4		0.94	0.96	10.62	10.62	0.08	
21720	Pond #3 Site 3 Sample1		1.01	0.73	11.41	11.41	1.01	
21800	Pond #3 Site 3 Sample 2		1.90	0.68	10.88	10.88	5.88	
21880	Pond # 3 Site 3 Sample 3		0.98	0.67	10.62	10.62	9.67	
21960	Pond # 3 Site 3 Sample 4		1.12	0.81	12.10	12.10	1.21	
22120	Pond # 2 Water LB		1.42	0.88	13.70	13.70	0.85	
22200	Pond # 2 Water LB		1.83	0.89	14.10	14.10	0.73	
23320	Pond # 3 Water LB		1.88	0.91	15.60	15.60	0.79	

Checked By:
 Date: 05/09/16

Approved By:
 Date: 08/09/16

ANALYSIS DEPARTMENT
 PNG UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY
 LAE
 MOROBE PROVINCE

CULTURE DEPARTMENT
 PNG UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY
 LAE
 MOROBE PROVINCE

Water samples data

UNITECH ANALYTICAL SERVICES LABORATORY

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CHEMICAL ANALYSIS REPORT

CLIENT: Mr Jerry Ferriwok
Post Graduate Student
C/- Department of Civil Engineering
PM3, PNGUOT

Page 1 of 2

ATTN: Dr. Betasolo

ORDER NO: LR-005

JOB ID: JCS-20

DATE: 7 Sep 2020

LAB No	CLIENT ID	TEST	Total Arsenic	Total Cadmium	Total Copper	Total Chromium
		UNITS	mg/L	mg/L	mg/L	mg/L
		METHOD	HNO ₃	HNO ₃	HNO ₃	HNO ₃
		BY	ICPOES	ICPOES	ICPOES	ICPOES
18020	Round Wara Sample#1 Site#1 Outlet		< 0.05	< 0.01	0.01	< 0.01
18120	Round Wara Sample#2 Site#1 (L/S)		< 0.05	< 0.01	0.01	< 0.01
18220	Round Wara Sample # 3 Site # 1 (R/S)		< 0.05	0.13	< 0.01	< 0.01
18320	Round Wara Sample # 4 Site #2 Center (R/S)		< 0.05	0.08	< 0.01	< 0.01
18420	Round Wara Sample # 5 Site 3 Center (L/S)		< 0.05	< 0.01	< 0.01	< 0.01
18520	Round Wara Sample #6 Site# 4 Inlet		< 0.05	0.09	< 0.01	< 0.01
18620	Round Wara Sample # 7 Site # 4 Inlet (R/S)		< 0.05	< 0.01	< 0.01	0.08
18720	Round Wara Sample # 8 Site # 4 Inlet (L/S)		< 0.05	< 0.01	< 0.01	< 0.01
18820	Sample # 1 Site 1 (Pond 1) Inlet		< 0.05	0.01	0.05	0.27
18920	Sample # 2 Site # 1 (Pond 1) R/S		< 0.05	< 0.01	0.06	0.02
19020	Sample 3 Site #1 (Pond 1) Outlet		< 0.05	< 0.01	0.13	0.14
19120	Sample 4 Site # 1 (Pond 1) L/S		< 0.05	< 0.01	< 0.01	0.15
19220	Sample 5 Site 2 (Pond 2) Inlet		< 0.05	0.02	0.08	0.21
19320	Sample 6 Site 2 (Pond 2) R/S		0.09	0.01	0.33	0.23
19420	Sample 7 Site 2 (Pond 2) Outlet		< 0.05	0.02	0.04	0.12

Checked By:

Date: 07/09/2020

Approved By:

Date: 07/09/2020

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CHEMICAL ANALYSIS REPORT

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SAMPLE ID		TEST	Total Arsenic	Total Cadmium	Total Copper	Total Chromium
		UNITS	mg/L	mg/L	mg/L	mg/L
LAB No.	CLIENT ID	METHOD	HNO ₃	HNO ₃	HNO ₃	HNO ₃
		BY	ICPOES	ICPOES	ICPOES	ICPOES
19520	Sample 8 Site 2 (Pond 2) L/S		< 0.05	< 0.01	0.13	3.11
19620	Sample 9 Site 3 (Pond 3) Inlet		< 0.05	< 0.01	0.13	3.18
19720	Sample 10 Site 3 (Pond 3) R/S		< 0.05	0.01	0.12	3.15
19820	Sample 11 Site 3 (Pond 3) Outlet		< 0.05	< 0.01	0.11	< 0.01
19920	Sample 12 Site 3 (Pond 3) L/S		< 0.05	0.01	0.16	3.15
20020	Sample 13 Site 4 Main outlet		< 0.05	< 0.01	0.07	< 0.01

"We certify that the values reported above were obtained using the appropriate standard operational procedures applicable to the samples submitted".

AGRICULTURE DEPARTMENT
 PAPUA NEW GUINEA
 UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY
 PMB
 LAE
 PAPUA NEW GUINEA

Checked By:

Approved By:

Date: 07/09/2020

Date: 07/09/2020

Identified individual plants data with its concentration uptake in mg/L

Sample ID	Species name	As (mg/L)	Cd (mg/L)	Cu (mg/L)	Cr (mg/L)
RWS1S1O	<i>Axonopus compressiu</i>	0.07	0.1	8.21	0.88
RWS1S2LS	<i>Amaranthus spinosus</i>	0.04	0.04	5.56	0.82
RWS1S3RH	<i>Megathyrus maximus</i>	0.03	0.1	7.23	0.87
RWS2S4RH	<i>Urochola maxima</i>	0.06	0.05	6.17	0.52
RWS3S5LH	<i>Eluensine indica</i>	0.02	0.03	5.98	0.49
RWS4S6IRH	<i>Cynodon dactylon</i>	0.01	0.02	4.33	0.22
RWS4S7IIH	<i>Impomea aquatica</i>	0.02	0.02	4.54	0.24
RWS4S8ILH	<i>Ageratum conyzoides</i>	0.02	0.01	4.61	0.23
		0.03375	0.04625	5.82875	0.53375
P1S1S1	<i>Cynodon dactylon</i>	0.78	0.23	7.28	0.12
P1S1S2	<i>Cynodon dactylon</i>	0.53	0.92	6.87	0.48
P1S1S3	<i>Cynodon dactylon</i>	0.48	0.94	7.41	0.52
P1S1S4	<i>Cynodon dactylon</i>	0.91	0.89	7.53	0.88
		0.675	0.745	7.2725	0.5
P2S2S1	<i>Cynodon dactylon</i>	0.92	0.87	9.29	1.01
P2S2S2	<i>Cynodon dactylon</i>	0.52	0.83	8.12	0.97
P2S2S3	<i>Cynodon dactylon</i>	0.53	0.84	8.1	0.94
P2S2S4	<i>Cynodon dactylon</i>	0.94	0.96	10.62	0.88
		0.7275	0.875	9.0325	0.95
P3S3S1	<i>Cynodon dactylon</i>	1.01	0.27	11.41	1.01
P3S3S2	<i>Cynodon dactylon</i>	1	0.68	10.88	9.88
P3S3S3	<i>Cynodon dactylon</i>	0.98	0.67	10.62	9.67
P3S3S4	<i>Cynodon dactylon</i>	1.12	0.81	12.1	1.21
		1.0275	0.6075	11.2525	5.4425
P1 w/lili	<i>Eichorina crassipes</i>	1.42	0.88	13.7	0.65
P2 w/Lili	<i>Eichorina crassipes</i>	1.83	0.89	14.1	0.73
P3w/lili	<i>Eichorina crassipes</i>	1.88	0.91	15.6	0.79
		1.71	0.893333	14.4666667	0.72

Photos of vegetation at sewage pond by Charles Feriwok

Photos of common weeds at swage pond by Charles Feriwok

Some of the most dominant weed species or water plants that are identified and collected for testing at site 1 sewage ponds.

Oxonopus compressus

Eichornia crassipe

Site 2 control site (Raunwara)

Sita acuta

Euphrasia hetrophyla

Amaranthus spinosus

Agerantum conyzoide

Ipomea aquatica

Oxonopus compressus

Eleusine indica

Photos of samples prepared for further testing

Soil samples

Weed samples